

**University of
Sunderland**

**Should the law on gross negligence
manslaughter be reformed in order to avoid
over-criminalisation of medical professionals?**

Criminal Law and Procedure LLM

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Should the law on gross negligence manslaughter be reformed in order to avoid over-criminalisation of medical professionals?

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Checklist (In the order it should appear in your submission).

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Abstract

If a doctor breaches their duty of care and death results, the doctor may not only be civilly liable but also prosecuted for gross negligence manslaughter, a crime with a maximum sentence of life imprisonment. This is despite the fact that there was no intention, nor even recklessness, in fact no real ‘guilty mind’, just an objective breach of the standard of care. This undermines the basic principles of criminal law. Since the recent case of *R v Rose*, a subjective element has been introduced, namely the foresight of harm. However, in theory, a truly incompetent doctor would therefore not be guilty as they did not foresee harm yet a more competent doctor would be. This seems a strange outcome.

Moreover, to be found guilty, it is for the jury to decide if that breach was so serious, so ‘gross’, that it warrants being a crime, yet there are no legal guidelines, it is left to their ‘common sense’. This is arbitrary, with no obvious consistency from one case to the next. Furthermore, the doctor may be found guilty even though it is clear that doctors work in very complex situations, as part of a far bigger team, under high pressure, dependent on other parts of the hospital, and errors can be due to a myriad of factors, as shown in the recent *Bawa-Garba* case. Indeed, the criminal offence makes no distinction between a simple one-off error by a doctor obliged to work long hours and under intense pressure to hit time targets, and a doctor who systematically cuts corners and breaches normal practice. As recent independent reports have established, this has left many medical practitioners feeling unfairly targeted. Patient safety, they claim, is being affected.

This paper analyses the crime of gross negligence manslaughter for medical practitioners, the current problems, and whether they are over-criminalised as a result.

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Hadiza Bawa-Garba v The General Medical Council [2018] EWCA Civ 1879

Montgomery v Lanarkshire Health Board [2015] UKSC 11

Nettleship v Weston [1971] 2 QB 691

R v Prentice [1993] 3 WLR 927

Rex v Murphy, 49 Ir. L. T. Rep. 15, 208 (1914)

R v Adomako (1994) 3 WLR 288, [1995] 1 A.C. 171

R v Bateman [1925] 19 Cr App R 8

R v Bawa-Garber, 4th Nov. 2015, (unreported), Nottingham Crown Court; leave to appeal refused in R v Bawa-Garba (Hadiza) [2016] EWCA Crim 1841

R v Kennedy [2007] UKHL 38

R v Lamb [1967] 2 QB 981

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R v Seymour [1983] 2 AC 493

R v Wacker [2003] QB 1203

R v Winterton [2018] EWCA Crim 2435

Sellu v The Crown [2016] EWCA Crim 1716

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Abdul Aziz

Chapter 1 – Introduction

This study focuses on the crime of gross negligence manslaughter (GNM) as applied to the medical profession. With no intent or even recklessness needed, medical professionals risk very serious criminal charges for acts of negligence. As recent caselaw shows, in an extremely busy environment, this negligence can be due to a myriad of factors, not just the doctors' own actions. It also undermines doctors' confidence in the system, risks alienating good doctors and even risking patient safety. It is therefore important to assess whether the crime of GNM is appropriate for the medical profession.

1.1 - Background

The common law offence of GNM is a form of involuntary manslaughter. As per *R v Bateman* [1925], it covers behavior that shows ‘such disregard for the life and safety of others as to amount to a crime against the state and conduct deserving of punishment’.¹ The case of *R v Adomako* (1994)² lays down the basic requirements, namely a breach of duty of care that causes death and which is so serious as to warrant criminal prosecution.

The issue is that the offence also applies to medical professionals carrying out their duties. However, the problem is that ‘medical mistakes come in many shapes and sizes yet criminal law adopts a one size fits all approach’.³ This does not seem appropriate. As shown in recent caselaw, in particularly the case of *R v Rose* [2017],⁴ and that of *R v Bawa-Garba (Hadiza)* [2016],⁵ the conviction of a doctor or a medical professional is an extremely serious, career-ending event, yet culpability is often directly linked to the pressure of work, as well as all the surrounding circumstances in the work environment. Furthermore, there

¹ *R v Bateman* [1925] 19 Cr App R 8

² *R v Adomako* (1994) 3 WLR 288

³ Oliver Quick, 'Medicine, Mistakes and Manslaughter: A Criminal Combination?' (2010) 69 Cambridge Law Journal 186, 187

⁴ *R v Rose* [2017] EWCA Crim 1168

⁵ *R v Bawa-Garber*, 4th Nov. 2015, (unreported), Nottingham Crown Court; leave to appeal refused in *R v Bawa-Garba (Hadiza)* [2016] EWCA Crim 1841.

is no requirement for intention, either direct or oblique, nor even recklessness. The trial judge for Dr. Bawa-Garber stated that the Children’s Assessment Unit was very busy and understaffed, there was no evidence that the doctor was “lazy or behaved for other selfish reasons”, blood results came back very late, there were numerous serious failings of the nurse, and the doctor had an unblemished record.⁶ And yet she was convicted of a very serious crime. Several important recent reviews have highlighted the negative effect that criminalising doctors in this fashion is having.

1.2 - The Legal Issues

This research highlights the dilemma of criminalising doctors and provides an assessment of the law on gross negligence as applied to medical professionals. As this is common law, it revolves primarily around caselaw. The central question is are medical professionals over-criminalised? And, if so, how the law should be reformed? In particular, if statutory intervention is required.

One important question is whether accountability and responsibility should be appropriately divided between health care systems, managers and doctors, rather than leaving the individual to bear all the blame.⁷ Is the current system of criminalising doctors “fraught with ethical tensions at levels of individual blameworthiness?”, as Samanta argues.⁸

The level of knowledge required is also important. In certain complicated cases, the risk of death may not be clear to the doctor, therefore the assumption of criminal liability should not fall on the doctor. After *R v Rose* [2017],⁹ it now seems that the serious risk of death must have been actually known/foreseeable to the accused, not just *ought* to have been

⁶ Quoted in *Hadiza Bawa-Garba v The General Medical Council* [2018] EWCA Civ 1879, para 18

⁷ A. Samanta, J. Samanta, ‘Gross negligence manslaughter and doctors: ethical concerns following the case of Dr Bawa-Garba’ (2019) 45 *Journal of Medical Ethics* 10,14

⁸ *Ibid*

⁹ See n. 4

known. However, as Mullock points out, this means that gross negligence in failing to assess risk in the first place is exonerated.¹⁰ This is inconsistent and surely not the intended consequence.

A more general question is whether medical professionals should be criminalised at all for negligence and, if so, under what circumstances. This begs an analysis of what criminalisation sets out to achieve and the different scholarly theories. It also requires an assessment of reasons against criminalisation of people performing a public service. This includes public policy reasons such as doctor recruitment, patient safety, public trust, to name a few.

The degree of ‘grossness’ for gross negligence manslaughter is obviously central to the issue too. It is important for doctors not to be seen to be above the law and yet it is important that there is transparency on how serious the degree of negligence has to be in order to warrant prosecution. The question is whether “the legal bar for convicting a medical professional of manslaughter in England and Wales should be raised to avoid good doctors being criminalised for mistakes”, as Bostock claims.¹¹

1.3 - Rationale of The Research Subject

This study is very topical. Following the recent cases of *R v Rose* [2017]¹² and *R v Bawa-Garba (Hadiza)* [2016],¹³ and the involvement of both the Crown Prosecution system and the General Medical Council (GMC), the medical profession claim that they feel

¹⁰ Alexandra Mullock, ‘Gross Negligence (Medical) Manslaughter and the Puzzling Implications of Negligent Ignorance: *Rose v R* [2017] EWCA Crim 1168’ (2018) 26 *Medical Law Review* 346,356

¹¹ Nick Bostock, ‘Raise legal bar to avoid criminalising good doctors for mistakes, warns MP’ (GP, 13 March 2018) available at < <https://www.gponline.com/raise-legal-bar-avoid-criminalising-good-doctors-mistakes-warns-mps/article/1459314>> accessed 17 June 2019

¹² See n. 4

¹³ See n. 5

victimized, at risk and there is a ‘toxic fear of reprisals’ if mistakes are made.¹⁴ This fear among medical professionals also poses a danger to them in the practice of the profession, which leads to fear in the orientation of the medical profession as well as this fear driven by the end of work because of error and imprisonment.¹⁵

This problem has been recognized by the review committees set up to address the issue. However, as stated in the 2018 Williams review,¹⁶ “This review was not set up to recommend changes in the law but to look at how decisions are made within the current legal framework”. Similarly, the 2019 Hamilton review¹⁷ states that considering changes to the law are not within its ‘remit or competence’. As such, this study aims to fill that gap and provide a review of the actual offence itself and its possible reform.

1.4 - Literature Review

As GNM is a common law offence, this research will provide detailed analysis of the existing caselaw, in particular the founding cases of *R v Bateman* [1925]¹⁸ and *R v Adomako* (1994),¹⁹ and the recent cases of *R v Rose* [2017]²⁰ and *R Bawa-Garba* [2016].²¹ The level of ‘seriousness’ required will be focused on, using cases such as *Sellu v The Crown* [2016],²² as well as the CA judgment in *R v Winterton* [2018].²³

The 2018 Williams review,²⁴ commissioned by the Secretary of State for Health, will be critically analysed. Also, the 2019 Hamilton review,²⁵ commissioned by the GMC,

¹⁴ Sarah Boseley, ‘Medical watchdog GMC needs to regain trust of doctors, finds review’ The Guardian, (6 June 2019), available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2019/jun/06/report-calls-for-reform-of-uk-medical-watchdog-to-regain-doctors-trust> accessed 17 June 2019

¹⁵ J.R. Spencer, ‘Prosecuting medical professionals for manslaughter’ 2 (2019) Archbold Review, 9

¹⁶ Sir Norman Williams, ‘Gross Negligence Manslaughter in Healthcare’, 2018, p. 9

¹⁷ Leslie Hamilton, ‘Independent Review of Gross Negligence Manslaughter and Culpable Homicide’, 2019 p.7

¹⁸ See n. 1

¹⁹ See n. 2

²⁰ See n. 4

²¹ See n. 5

²² *Sellu v The Crown* [2016] EWCA Crim 1716

²³ *R v Winterton* [2018] EWCA 2435 (Crim)

²⁴ Williams, See n. 16

²⁵ Hamilton, See n. 17

published only two weeks ago from the beginning of this study. These provide an important understanding of the legal practices and approach, as well as the concerns and impact on healthcare professionals.

Academic and scholarly articles will also be used. Dr Anne Lodge writes that “There is no comprehensible and consistent means of measuring whether conduct is sufficiently gross to warrant criminal conviction”.²⁶ She adds that “The gross negligence condition also sets the culpability bar too low”.²⁷ Oliver Quick’s examination in the Cambridge Law Journal is particularly interesting,²⁸ arguing that a degree of subjective recklessness should be required. The other articles mentioned above also add much debate.

1.5 - Research Methodology

This research will essentially rely on an analysis by the doctrinal research methodology; as such, using the black letter law method, this study will benefit from detailed analysis of primary documents such as case law and judicial decisions: the "doctrinal method lies at the basis of the common law and is the core legal research method".²⁹ This will be followed by an analysis study using secondary sources such as scholarly journals, books and official reports including government reports and professional body reports, as well as newspaper articles and relevant websites for the most recent developments.

²⁶ Anne Lodge, ‘Gross negligence manslaughter on the cusp: the unprincipled privileging of harm over culpability’ (2017) 81 *Journal of Criminal Law* 125,142

²⁷ *Ibid*

²⁸ Quick, See n. 3

²⁹ Nigel Duncan & Terry Hutchinson, 'Defining and describing what we do: Doctrinal legal research' (2012) 17 *DLR* 83,119

1.6 - Intended Outcomes

The research study intends to produce a review of the current law and to consider reforms about the criminalisation of medical professionals in relation to gross negligence manslaughter. It will question whether it is important to reduce this risk to protect those who work in this field or whether this will seem to be putting doctors above the law. The aim is to provide a comprehensive review of both legal and policy considerations regarding medical professionals and their potential culpability for death where, unintentionally, their actions have fallen far below the standard required. Recommendations will be made for reform. It is hoped that this will be a useful resource for both legal and medical professional bodies.

Chapter 2 - Medical Professionals and Their Criminalisation for Gross Negligence Manslaughter

It is obvious that, even if they have the best of intentions, doctors cannot be given complete legal freedom and be unaccountable. However, the question is whether the criminal offence of GNM is appropriate for those in a medical profession or they are over criminalised. The following section will comprehensively discuss the aspects of the crime as pertaining to the medical profession, along with some tests that are conducted to deal with the level of care needed, like the Bolam test. An assessment of several recent controversial cases as regards GNM in the medical field will also be presented.

2.1 - The Criminal Offence of Gross Negligence Manslaughter

Both murder and manslaughter involve the unlawful killing of another human being. The *actus reus* is therefore the same. However, manslaughter is a far broader category, encompassing both voluntary and involuntary. The basic difference in the elements of the two crimes is the fact that involuntary manslaughter does not require the *Mens rea* of murder, namely the intention to cause death or serious harm.³⁰ More specifically, voluntary manslaughter is generally a 'picture' of murder, but because of certain circumstances such as provocation, it softens to manslaughter, whereas involuntary manslaughter is simply the absence of intent to cause the death or serious injury of a person.³¹ Under involuntary manslaughter, however, there are two general sub-categories: unlawful act manslaughter and gross negligence manslaughter. This research concerns the latter. The involuntary manslaughter due to gross negligence lies at the bottom of the pyramid of homicide,³² and is defined as "The defendant's behaviour caused danger in the death of a person, which was clear to a reasonable person in the same situation, in addition to the behaviour of the defendant who was less than expected under these circumstances and who should have

³⁰ William Wilson, *Criminal Law* (6th edn, Pearson 2017)

³¹ Geoff Holgate, 'Reforming the Law on Involuntary Manslaughter' (2000) 164 J.P. 894

³² Lodge, See n. 26

assessed the risk”.³³ As such, although negligence, namely a breach of duty of care that causes harm, is a civil concept, GNM criminalises the most serious breaches in this duty of care that result in death.

It is worth mentioning that most parts of law are ‘handicapped’ and need words of interpretation. This is an obstacle to involuntary manslaughter that has been rampant, because of what the Law Commission calls the crime’s ‘uncertainty’ and ‘lack of any clear conceptual vocabulary’.³⁴ Indeed, GNM is in the ‘worst’ situation,³⁵ as the House of Lords addressed the law in 1983,³⁶ but the Court of Appeal then gave up what the House of Lords had called for in the case of *R v Prentice* [1993].³⁷ The question, therefore, is whether this criminalisation is the appropriate response, in particular to the medical profession, and, if so, what the criteria ought to be.

2.1.1 - Requirements of The Offence

The basic requirements of the crime of GNM were laid out in 1925 by Lord Hewart CJ, namely a breach of an established duty of care, under civil law, must be committed by the suspect, causing death and furthermore, that this breach was of sufficient seriousness to amount to a “crime against the State and conduct deserving punishment”, as determined by the jury.³⁸

The case that can be used as a modern reference is the case of *R v Adomako* [1995]³⁹ where an anaesthetist was prosecuted for GNM because of a breach in his duties during the eye surgery of a patient. During the surgery, one of the essential ventilator tubes got disconnected, the doctor failed to notice, and the patient suffered a fatal heart attack.

³³ Wilson, See n. 30

³⁴ Law Commission, Involuntary Manslaughter (Law Com No 135, 1994) paras 1.22

³⁵ Ibid. para 1.23

³⁶ *R v Seymour* [1983] 2 AC 493

³⁷ *R v Prentice* [1993] 3 WLR 927

³⁸ See n. 1, 10-12

³⁹ *R v Adomako* [1995] 1 A.C. 171

The court held was that the anaesthetist was guilty and should have been more careful as he knew that the surgery is critical. His appeal to the House of Lords was unanimously dismissed.⁴⁰

Following the Adomako case, three points must be established. As Lord Mackay of Clashfern LC said, the first question is whether, under the ordinary rules of negligence, a duty of care existed and was breached; the second question is whether that breach caused the death; and thirdly the jury have to consider whether that breach was of such a serious nature as to be “characterised as gross negligence and therefore as a crime”⁴¹. This third point is the most problematic.

At the time of treatment, therefore, there are generally accepted medical practice procedures that should be followed (i.e. as exemplified or recognised by an approved medical body).⁴² The doctor in charge of the treatment did not use the above-mentioned practical procedures; and doctors with normal skills, if they act with a general caution, would not use the treatment methods used by the doctors involved.⁴³

If all these requirements are not followed by the doctors, and death results, and then they may face a charge of manslaughter due to gross negligence.⁴⁴

⁴⁰ See n. 39

⁴¹ Ibid

⁴² H. Beckett, and J. Radford. ‘ 'Montgomery consent': decision of the UK Supreme Court. *Montgomery v Lanarkshire Health Board*. [2015] UKSC 11; [2015] WLR 768.’ (2016) 19 *The practising midwife* 27,29

⁴³ Gwen Adshead, David Crepaz-Keay, Mayura Deshpande, KWM Bill Fulford, and Veryan Richards. ‘Montgomery and shared decision-making: implications for good psychiatric practice.’ (2018) 213 *The British Journal of Psychiatry* 630,632

⁴⁴ Adrian Hărățău, ‘Theoretical and case-law considerations on the professional negligence of doctors that could result in criminal, not only civil, liability.’ (2017) 7 *Challenges of the Knowledge Society* 166,173

2.1.2 - Duty of Care

The duty of care is the first element that the prosecution must prove in GNM.⁴⁵ A duty of care is owed, as per the classic tort cases of *Donoghue v Stevenson* [1932],⁴⁶ with Lord Atkin's neighbour principle, and the Caparo test,⁴⁷ where there must be foreseeability, proximity and fairness. The first two criteria are not an issue in a medical situation: it is obvious that it is foreseeable that a doctor's actions could cause damage, and the relationship between doctor and patient is close. The third criterion is not a potential problem either: it seems fair, just and reasonable to impose a duty of care on the doctor, given the importance of their role, the trust placed in them, and the health trust insurance, and they should therefore be liable in civil law if that duty is breached and causes harm.

However, this is not the same as criminal guilt. The question of duty of care in a criminal situation appears in *R v Wacker* [2003],⁴⁸ where a person illegally smuggled 60 people into a container, but the air was closed off and caused death. The duty of care here was owed to the victims by the offender and the sentence by the Crown Court was that of gross negligence manslaughter, as the negligence was of such a serious degree that criminalisation was warranted. The important question is where to draw the line for this criminalisation, and whether it should be the same for medical professionals, trying to save lives, as the man who illegally smuggled the people into the container.⁴⁹

2.1.3 - Breach: The Standard of Care

Another issue that has much caselaw for medical professionals focuses on the fact that in order to determine whether there has been a breach of the duty of care, it is necessary to determine the standard of care. The standard of care owed is according to what was

⁴⁵ Hārātāu, See n. 44

⁴⁶ *Donoghue v Stevenson* [1932] AC 562

⁴⁷ *Caparo Industries PLC v Dickman* [1990] UKHL 2

⁴⁸ *R v Wacker* [2003] QB 1203

⁴⁹ Wilson, See n. 30

expected of a person in the same circumstances, not according to his qualifications or experience.⁵⁰

In *Bolam v Friern Hospital Management Committee* [1957],⁵¹ the judge explained that the doctor was not liable if he had performed an acceptable practice, saying: "a doctor is not guilty of negligence if he has acted in accordance with a practice accepted as proper by a responsible body of medical men skilled in that particular art putting it the other way round, a doctor is not negligent, if he is acting in accordance with such a practice, merely because there is a body of opinion that takes a contrary view ".⁵² Just as the standard of care that is breached is the same as in civil law, it is objectively determined.⁵³

Accordingly, doctors are usually liable for negligence in two situations, first, negligence in the execution of medical procedures and second, the risk of not disclosing medical procedures to patients when seeking medical consent from the patient,⁵⁴ as per *Montgomery v Lanarkshire Health Board* [2015].⁵⁵

According to the Bolam test, doctors who do not act as appropriate in accordance with the medical staff's responsibility to organise acceptance are considered to be negligent.⁵⁶ This means that if a responsible body of medical opinion backs the doctor's judgment, even if his practice was not normal procedure, the doctor has not breached his/her duty of care. However, 'body' is not quantified so, effectively, one or two expert opinions, backing that doctor at fault, will be sufficient. The opportunity for doctors clubbing together to protect one another and thereby excluding the judge, is obvious.

⁵⁰ Witting Christian, 'National Health Service Rationing: Implications for the Standard of Care in Negligence' (2001) 21 Oxford J Legal Studies 443

⁵¹ *Bolam v Friern Hospital Management Committee* [1957] 1 WLR 582

⁵² *Ibid*

⁵³ Wilson, See n. 30

⁵⁴ Rob Heywood, "'If The Problem Persists, Come Back to See Me...'"—An Empirical Study of Clinical Negligence Cases Against General Practitioners.' (2018) 27 Medical law review 406,431

⁵⁵ *Montgomery v Lanarkshire Health Board* [2015] UKSC 11

⁵⁶ *Ibid*

However, the “Bolam Test” is no longer applicable in the same form in the UK, having been modified by the Bolitho test,⁵⁷ whereby the House of Lords held that there had to be a logical basis for the decision, as determined by law and not the medical profession itself. This is to be welcomed as logical explanations should be possible and medical professions cannot simply expect to have their word accepted. The Bolam test therefore is no longer valid for serious cases in the UK but remains relevant in case of diagnosis, treatment and other medical negligence.⁵⁸

The Sidaway ruling, however, adopted the Bolam test as a suitable test in order to get better results. Therefore, it is required to consider all the aspects,⁵⁹ for instance, to check whether the medical staff has been informed about the risk of negligence in the healthcare industry so that they can learn the ways to prevent these risks.⁶⁰ In recent years, patient organisations have asked health care workers to disclose information more fully and to promote proper communication between doctors and patients. In order to more effectively reflect the change in social values, the Medical Council has amended the Code of Practice, in particular, Article 2.10.2, to include the requirement that doctors should provide medical services and communicate with patients depending on the individual circumstances of each patient.⁶¹ If following the ruling of the Supreme Court of the United Kingdom in the Montgomery case, the Bolam test will no longer apply to the determination of whether medical staff are negligent in the disclosure of risks, but must be considered from the perspective of individual patients.⁶²

⁵⁷ Bolitho v City and Hackney Health Authority [1997] 4 All ER 771

⁵⁸ Jenny Vaughan, ““gross negligence manslaughter” and the healthcare professional.’ (2016) 98 The Bulletin of the Royal College of Surgeons of England 60,62

⁵⁹ Dennis J. Mazur, ‘High court decision making in informed consent: movement to the reasonable person in the patient’s position standard and a focus on severe adverse outcomes of low chance (probability) of the occurrence’ (2016) 12 International Journal of Ethics 165,170

⁶⁰ Julian C. Hughes, David Crepaz-Keay, Charlotte Emmett, and K. W. M. Fulford, ‘The Montgomery ruling, individual values and shared decision-making in psychiatry’ (2018) 24 BJPsych Advances 93,100

⁶¹ Rob. Heywood, ‘RIP Sidaway: patient-oriented disclosure—a standard worth waiting for? Montgomery v Lanarkshire Health Board [2015] UKSC 11.’ (2015) 23 Medical law review 455,466

⁶² See n. 39

Since the “Montgomery case”, number of new tests has been introduced after the Bolam test to enhance the process that are involved in the cases of medical disclosure and advice from health care professionals in the UK.⁶³ The “new test requirements that are should not only be considered from the perspective of the doctor”, but also from the perspective of the patient.⁶⁴ Although no cases have been decided by the new tests established in the Montgomery case so far, it is foreseeable that this “patient-oriented” test will be in court when there is a medical negligence case that neglects to provide information when seeking patient consent raised.⁶⁵

In summary, medical professionals who put themselves out as having a certain higher level will be expected to demonstrate a higher standard of care. This seems reasonable: although *Nettleship v Weston* [1971]⁶⁶ shows us the learner drivers and experienced drivers are to be treated the same in terms of their standard, this is because they are both simply ‘drivers’. A specific higher category of driver, however, would be different. Thus, a surgeon will be expected to act to a higher standard of care than a general practitioner, in regards to his/her special domain, namely that of the ‘reasonable’ surgeon. However, that standard of care will be breached even if other doctors may agree with the treatment given, if the judge cannot see a logical explanation for it.

2.1.4 - Death

GNM requires that the breach of the duty of care resulted in the death of the victim. This raises an anomaly, in that in English law there is no specific crime of causing serious bodily harm by gross negligence and is discussed in more length later.

⁶³ A. Coulter, A. Hopkins, and B. Moulton, ‘Montgomery v Lanarkshire Health Board: transforming informed consent.’ (2017) 99 *The Bulletin of the Royal College of Surgeons of England* 36,38.

⁶⁴ Lee Albert, ‘‘Montgomery’ case: the significant role of family physicians.’ (2016) 38 *Hong Kong Practitioner* 108,109

⁶⁵ Jean V. Mchale, ‘Innovation, informed consent, health research and the Supreme Court: Montgomery v Lanarkshire— a brave new world?’ (2017) 12 *Health Economics, Policy and Law* 435,452

⁶⁶ *Nettleship v Weston* [1971] 2 QB 691

2.1.5 - ‘Gross’ Negligence That Warrants Being a Crime

This is one of the most problematic elements of the crime. It is this that turns civil liability into criminal guilt. In Adomako, the judge gave the following guidelines:

“This will depend on the seriousness of the breach of duty committed by the defendant in all the circumstances in which the defendant was placed when it occurred. The jury will have to consider whether the extent to which the defendant’s conduct departed from the proper standard of care incumbent upon him, involving as it must have done a risk of death to the patient, was such that it should be judged criminal.”⁶⁷

As such, the question of intent and/or recklessness is extremely important. Criminal law is based on the importance of a ‘guilty mind’, the *mens rea* that makes a simple act a crime. Almost 100 years ago, Bishop wrote that “there can be no crime large or small, without an evil mind”.⁶⁸ Based on the requirements above, however, no intention as such is needed for GNM, nor even recklessness. Rather, the *mens rea* in GNM, insofar as there is any, is simply that the suspect “showed such disregard for the life and safety of others as to amount to a crime against the State and conduct deserving punishment”, as stated in Bateman.⁶⁹ Negligence, as established under the principles of tort, and compensation under civil law, is not the question. Dr. Adomako, for instance, readily admitted negligence. Rather the aim of the criminal law is to punish the wrongful acts of GNM more than to have civil claims against the offender,⁷⁰ and this requires negligence of such a serious nature, so ‘gross’, that it lifts it out of civil law and makes it a crime. This is analysed in more detail later. However, as the Law Commission accepted, the judge’s guidelines are, effectively, circular and provide very little practical guidance.⁷¹

⁶⁷ See n. 39

⁶⁸ Joel Prentiss Bishop, ‘*Criminal Law*’ (9th edn, TH Flood, 1923)

⁶⁹ See n. 1, Lord Hewart C.J. pp. 10-11

⁷⁰ Child John, and Ormerod David, *Smith & Hogan’s Essentials of Criminal Law* (1st edn, Oxford 2015)

⁷¹ Law Com, See n. 34

2.2 - Modern Caselaw Developments in GNM of The Medical Field

In applying these criteria to the medical profession, the courts seem to oscillate between sympathy for doctors and treating medical GNM as no different from any other. It should be remembered that in what is generally considered to be the first case of medical GNM, *R v Bateman* [1925]⁷², the doctor's guilty verdict was overturned by the Court of Appeal. In that case, a healthcare practitioner was sentenced for GNM following the case of childbirth where after the delivery, the practitioner had used considerable force, the child was dead, and, furthermore, the practitioner unknowingly removed the part of the uterus, and failed to transfer the mother quickly to the infirmary which led to the death of the patient.⁷³ However, the guilty verdict was quashed by the Court of Appeal as the judge of first instance had directed the jury incorrectly as to the different *mens rea* for civil and criminal liability. This sympathy with doctors as a professional body can be seen through much of English caselaw, as shown also in the Bolam case above. There is an obvious reluctance on the part of the judiciary to hold doctors accountable when acting in good faith for the benefit of their patients, even if mistakes occur.

However, this tendency seems to have been inverted in recent decades. In *R v Misra and Srivastava* [2005]⁷⁴ two practitioners were convicted for GNM because the patient they were operating on got diseased with infections, the infection was untreated and the patient died.

More recently, however, it has seemed more mixed, with much discussion centred on two important and controversial cases. An important legal issue in *R v Rose* [2017] was the level of knowledge of death or serious injury that is required.⁷⁵ In certain medical cases, the risk of death, or serious injury, may not be clear to the doctor. The question has to be assessed objectively and prospectively. The optometrist in this case was acquitted on

⁷² See n. 1

⁷³ Sarah W. Chan, Ed Tulloch, E. Sarah Cooper, Andrew Smith, Wojtek Wojcik, and Jane E. Norman 'Montgomery and informed consent: where are we now?' (BMJ, 12 May 2017) available at <<https://www.bmj.com/content/357/bmj.j2224>> accessed 2 July 2019

⁷⁴ *R v Misra and Srivastava* [2005] 1 Cr App R 328

⁷⁵ See n. 4

appeal, after the CoA established that the correct question was what risk was reasonably foreseeable at the time of the risk, *not* what risk would have been foreseeable but for the breach. However, it was accepted that Rose did not examine the eye properly, and if she had, the signs of brain condition from which the person died, would have been obvious. But the fact that she did not meant that the risk was not known.

After the case of *R v Rose* [2017],⁷⁶ it now seems that the serious risk of death must have been actually known/foreseeable to the accused, not just *ought* to have been known. This is highly debateable: indeed, the Court of Appeal specifically accepted the serious negligence of Rose but stated that the: “serious breach of duty is a matter for her regulator; in the context of this case, however, it does not constitute the crime of gross negligence manslaughter”.⁷⁷ The problem of *mens rea*, intention and recklessness, (or lack of it) as mentioned above, seems clear. Yet this is not required, per se, in the offence.

More controversy surrounds the case of *Hadiza Bawa-Garba v The General Medical Council* [2018]⁷⁸. In this case, the issue was that junior doctor faced prosecution for GNM because the boy died when he was in charge of the unit. The patient’s family member told the junior doctor that the patient was not responding properly after the surgery, but due to the junior doctor's negligence, the boy died. The court highlighted a number of ethical issues raised in the case because of the negligence of the junior doctor. Moreover, the hospital trust itself was shown to have problems with systems and procedures, which were also instrumental in the death; these, however, were not a defence for the accused. Therefore, the licence of the medical professional was cancelled by the Medical Practitioners Tribunals and she was found guilty of the offence of GNM.

⁷⁶ See n. 4

⁷⁷ Mullock, See n. 10

⁷⁸ *Hadiza Bawa-Garba v The General Medical Council* [2018] EWCA Civ 1879

2.3 - The Medical Profession: Reaction and Statistics Concerning Gross Negligence Manslaughter

The reaction of the medical profession to the arguably overly heavy-handed attack on Dr. Bawa-Garber has given a lot of cause of concern, both to the medical and legal authorities. The issue of GNM as applied specifically to medical professionals is important as healthcare is such an important sector, both in terms of resources used and the impact on individuals' well-being. There are, of course, many regulatory bodies involved. The government of the UK designed a regulatory Professional Standards Authority (PSA) to manage healthcare institutions and other organisations in the UK.⁷⁹ In total, there are nine organisations that work under PSA and control medical professionals. Those nine organisations are “General Chiropractic Council, General Dental Council, General Osteopathic Council, Pharmaceutical Society of Northern Ireland, General Medical Council, General Pharmaceutical Council, Health and Care Professions Council, General Optical Council and Nursing and Midwifery Council”.⁸⁰

Because of the reaction to Bawa-Garber, two important public reports have been conducted: the 2018 Williams review and the 2019 Hamilton review. The Williams report,⁸¹ reviewed the process of investigating GNM in medical cases and “the wider patient safety impact of concerns among medical professionals that simple errors could result in prosecution for gross negligence manslaughter, even if they happen in the context of broader organisation and system failings”.⁸² According to the report, from 2013 until 2018, there has been more than 130 cases of GNM. In 2013, there were 18; in 2014, the cases rose to their peak, with more than 40. However, in 2018 after the strict laws and regulations, the UK witnessed the lowest cases of GNM at only 7.

⁷⁹ Wakeford Richard, ‘The professional standards authority watches the GMC, apparently’ (BMJ, 28 January 2015) available at <<https://www.bmj.com/content/350/bmj.h451>> accessed 10 July 2019

⁸⁰ Eirini Oikonomou, Jane Carthey, Carl Macrae, and Charles Vincent. ‘Patient safety regulation in the NHS: mapping the regulatory landscape of healthcare.’ (2019) 9 BMJ

⁸¹ Williams, See n. 16

⁸² Williams, See n. 16 p.9

It has also been reported that more than 30 patients have been the subject of prosecutions of GNM from 2010 in the UK.⁸³ More than 35 practitioners, one optometrist and five nurses have been the part of the cases of GNM in the UK and out of which more than 20 medical professionals were convicted.

2.4 - Conclusion

The chapter has highlighted the requirements of the offence of GNM which has no basis in statutory law, only common law, with few cases in the UK in general, and even less for the medical profession.⁸⁴ Medical professionals are one group of people who are particularly vulnerable to charges of GNM because medical professionals' duty is so complex that, if negligent, they can lose a life. However, as shown by the reaction to the Bawa-Garber case,⁸⁵ the risk of being criminalised places a very large burden on practitioners, over and above the burdens they carry on a daily basis as part of a high stress and vital profession. Furthermore, they do not act in isolation: as the William report says, medical professionals "work in complex, high-risk environments, invariably as part of a team, and when things go wrong it is rarely the result of one individual's error".⁸⁶ It does not seem right that doctors are victimised for mistakes that are part of a larger working practice issue. This will not help patient safety or encourage good new recruits into the profession. Indeed, it begs the question whether medical professionals, acting in good faith, should ever risk criminal prosecution. The next section of the research, therefore, will provide a comprehensive discussion on the criminal theories and criminal liability of medical professionals.

⁸³ Law Com, See n. 34

⁸⁴ Lucy Todd, Kenar Usman, Faye Tyler, Lily Toffolo, and Andrew Temple. 'Should the laws on involuntary manslaughter in England and Wales be reformed?' (2019) 1 *The Student Journal of Professional Practice and Academic Research* 66,73

⁸⁵ See n. 5

⁸⁶ Williams, See n. 16, n 67, p.5

Chapter 3 - The Criminalisation of Medical Professionals: The Theories

As Voltaire said (in approximate translation), “With great power comes great responsibility”.⁸⁷ As such, our medical profession has both great power in their hands but also the duty to assume great responsibility. However, if lapses occur in this great responsibility, it is not necessarily appropriate that this should result in criminal convictions. In order to analyse the crime of gross negligence manslaughter in relation to medical practitioners, it is necessary to review what criminal law, and the criminalisation of certain actions and not others, is trying to achieve. Indeed, there are many theories developed for criminalisation in general, developed by a range of scholars, but these theories do not necessarily suit the conditions of the medical profession.

This chapter therefore presents an analysis of the suitability of the over-arching reasons for criminalisation, such as punishment, protection for the public and the deterrence of such errors that may occur and lead to death, and to see whether the crime of GNM for medics achieves these aims of criminalisation.

3.1 - The Theory of Harm Principle

The basic starting point of criminal law has traditionally been founded on the harm theory. This theory is based on the basic principle that for the state's action to criminalise or punish an act, such act or behavior must cause harm to others.⁸⁸ This theory was first clarified and discussed by Mills: force should be used only for the sole purpose of preventing harm to others either physically or morally, and not to prevent people from any actions deemed acceptable by the state.⁸⁹ Under Mills' theory, therefore, people should be free to do things as long as they do not pose a danger harm to others. This theory in general promotes

⁸⁷ Voltaire, ‘Archives Parlementaires, Tome 64 : Du 2 au 16 mai 1793, Séance du mardi 7 mai 1793’ page 287, available at: https://frda.stanford.edu/fr/catalog/wx067jz0783_00_0293, accessed 20/08/19

⁸⁸ A P Simester, J R Spencer, F Stark, G R Sullivan and G J Virgo: *Simester and Sullivan's Criminal law theory and Doctrine* (6th edn, Hart publishing 2016)

⁸⁹ J.S. Mill, *On Liberty and Other Essays* (2nd edn, Oxford World's Classics 2008)

freedom and is intended to allow people to act freely without harm to others, while at the same time giving the option of actually doing anything, unless that may be a crime.⁹⁰ This theory, according to Feinberg, is of a simple nature, based on the fact that harm is only criminalised when danger is posed by another person.⁹¹

This seems suitable to the duty of the medical professional whose action is not intended to harm the patient. The criminalisation is here according to the harm, and the doctor in the case of treatment that may in certain situations cause harm or danger, but not with the intention of harm and that the patient's satisfaction is present here.⁹² Although there is academic argument as to the definition of 'harm, it is obvious that a doctor who, by negligence, has caused death has undeniably caused harm and this, therefore, satisfies the harm principle.

However, saying that an action must cause harm for it to be criminalised is not the same as saying that all actions that cause harm should be criminalised. As Herring writes, there are many actions that cause harm that are in no way a criminal act.⁹³ Indeed, many operations will, with hindsight, have caused harm but they were done with the aim of doing good and are not automatically criminal simply because they did not have the outcome people wanted. So, although the harm is easy to establish in GNM medical cases, this may be necessary, as a minimum requirement,⁹⁴ but it is not sufficient for criminalisation.

⁹⁰ William Wilson, *Criminal Law Doctrine and Theory* (4th edn, Pearson 2011)

⁹¹ Joel Feinberg, *The Moral Limits of the Criminal Law: Harm to Others: Harm to Others* (1st edn, Oxford University Press 1987)

⁹² Zane Robinson Wolf, 'Error Reporting and Disclosure' In Ronda G. Hughes (eds), *Patient Safety and Quality: An Evidence-Based Handbook for Nurses* (AHRQ 2008)

⁹³ Jonathan Herring, *Criminal Law*, (3rd edn, Palgrave 2015) p.10

⁹⁴ S.E. Marshall & R.A. Duff, 'Criminalization and Sharing Wrongs' (1998) 11 *Can J L & Juris* 7

3.2 - The Theory of Legal Moralism

This theory is based on the principle that criminal law is used precisely to criminalise or allow behavior based on the rules of society, on whether society sees this as moral or not.⁹⁵ So if society believes that a particular act may simply be unethical, even if not harmful, then this is criminal according to what the society sees. Feinberg explained that legal moralism is based on the fact that it "can be morally legitimate to prohibit conduct on the ground that it is inherently immoral, even though it causes neither harm nor offence to the actor or to others".⁹⁶ As such, it concerns what Duff calls "public wrongs" which are, he claims, analogous to professional misconduct, i.e. based on an accepted code of ethics in the profession, or society.⁹⁷ The legal moralism theory provides a strong reason for criminalisation and punishment, however the punishment is based on the moral view of society.⁹⁸ Basing law on morality finds support in legal judgments. Lord Simonds said the courts seek to impose moral order:

"there remains in the courts of law a residual power to enforce the supreme and fundamental purpose of the law, to conserve not only the safety and order but also the moral welfare of the state."⁹⁹

It would seem unlikely, however, that society views doctors acting in good faith, but making serious errors, as being 'immoral' as such. It is hardly unethical to make a genuine mistake, even if it has serious consequences. Indeed, the main aim of criminal liability for medical professionals is to look at whether they acted out of intention or not, because the work of medical professionals is considered *prima facie* ethical and the community views the doctor as a patient's savior. Indeed, the only legal recourse to legal morality, Feinberg

⁹⁵ Simester, See n. 88

⁹⁶ Feinberg, See n. 91

⁹⁷ R. A. Duff, *Introduction: A Theory of Criminalization? The Realm of Criminal Law* (Oxford University Press 2018)

⁹⁸ Simester, See n. 88

⁹⁹ *Shaw v DPP* [1962] AC 220, 267

argues, is to provide examples of actions that are counterproductive and that do not fall under the principle of harm and this may make the task of this theory difficult.¹⁰⁰

And many would say that immorality in itself is not even enough, nor even outrage. As Duff and Marshall write, it “requires more than a general feeling of outrage to characterise just what kinds of wrongs are appropriately categorised as crimes”.¹⁰¹ It is hard to see extreme ‘outrage’ as a reaction to a medical tragedy, even one caused by gross negligence, let alone some further and greater reaction. Therefore, legal moralism does not seem an appropriate basis.

However, although the act itself might not cause moral outrage, the death often does. The death in question is always that of an innocent. It is a person who is sick, who needed care, and who is let down by the very medics who are supposed to look after them. It is no surprise that the *R v Bawa-Garba (Hadiza)* [2016]¹⁰² case concerned a child of six, and the *R v Rose* [2017]¹⁰³ case a boy of eight: the children who died are the definition of innocence. Their deaths give rise to moral outcries, in and of themselves, even if the action that caused it is not immoral, pushing the government towards making it a criminal offence, judges to widen the scope and juries to convict.

This gives rise to a demand for retributive justice. As Oldenquist writes,¹⁰⁴ the “universal insistence upon retribution” is “deeply-felt” and “intractable”. And this often applies simply to the death, not to the supposed crime. It is a very emotional area. Families of children who have died unnecessarily often demand ‘justice’, by which they mean they want someone to ‘pay’. The family of Charlotte Howard claim that Jack Shepherd, recently convicted of gross negligence manslaughter, had “stolen a beautiful life”, that “if it wasn't for this our lovely Charlotte would still be here”, and that the Shepherd needed to

¹⁰⁰ Feinberg, See n. 91

¹⁰¹ Marshall & Duff, See n. 94

¹⁰² See n. 5

¹⁰³ See n. 4

¹⁰⁴ Andrew Oldenquist, 'An Explanation of Retribution' (1988) 85 the journal of philosophy 464,478

“atone”.¹⁰⁵ The family’s grief is acute and the public have (understandably) very little sympathy for the accused but a tragic and avoidable death does not always mean that, in law, there is a killer.

3.3 – The Punishment

One of the main aims of criminal law is to punish the offender. This is a rather old-fashioned, conservative religious approach, linked to legal moralism. Practically, from a punitive point of view, a punitive hypothesis is suitable for the criminal status of medical professionals who make grave errors. It is the death that is at the root - there has been an unnecessary death and a standard reaction is that someone should be punished for it. The error itself would not be criminal without the death.

If harm is a requisite, but not sufficient, and legal moralism relates more to the death than the action, there must be a further basis for criminalising GNM in general, and against doctors in particular. This thesis contends that the underlying principle is actually a ‘grey area’ that acts as a combination of the two. The fact that death has occurred is vital. It is important to note that there is no crime of ‘gross negligence serious bodily harm’. In the Offences Against the Person Act 1861, the *mens rea* needed has always been taken to be intent or recklessness.¹⁰⁶ This is contrary to many other countries where criminal negligence has separate status. In England, GNM has evolved because society views death differently and the fact that the harm is ‘death’, (often of an innocent sick child, as above), means there is more demand for answers, and for culpability. In short, people seem to demand retribution.

Punishing offenders is at the heart of many criminal systems. It appeals to the public in a rather basic, instinctive way, giving a simplistic answer to what happens to ‘bad’ people,

¹⁰⁵ Gareth Davies, ‘Family of woman who died in speedboat crash to meet Sajid Javid to demand update on her fugitive killer’, The Telegraph (London, 22 January 2019) <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2019/01/22/family-woman-died-speedboat-crash-meet-sajid-javid-demand-update> accessed 11 August 2019

¹⁰⁶ Offences Against the Person Act 1861

and backed up by easy mantras such as ‘do the crime, do the time’. It is based on retribution, an eye for an eye. As such, it is dangerously close to revenge.¹⁰⁷

However, as many scholars and researchers point out, it does not necessarily have good results, does not reduce crime going forward, just enables politicians to claim to be tough on crime which is a popular and vote-winning stand.¹⁰⁸ Indeed, in many cases, doctors’ fear of punishment or imprisonment as a result of court rulings may lead to a retreat of the doctor in the treatment or care of his/her patient due to some fear of punishment.¹⁰⁹ This may undermine patient safety, as discussed below. Nevertheless, this theory seems to be the most appropriate punishment because the society may consider professionals sympathetic as they are the noble profession, regardless of sympathy for the patient, but this may be a little appropriate for the doctor. However, punishment may constitute a fair kind of justice for medical professionals as long as it punishes in cases of gross negligence only, and this came on the heels of *R v Lowe* [1973] case¹¹⁰ which punished only for negligent manslaughter in gross negligence. Again, however, it revolves round the question of what constitutes ‘gross’.

The purpose of the punishment is also strongly linked to deterrence,¹¹¹ and the fact that the doctor who did the harm did not intend to harm, this theory provides him with the necessary protection from punishment that poses fears.¹¹²

¹⁰⁷ Oldenquist, See n. 104

¹⁰⁸ William Kelly, ‘Why Punishment Doesn’t Reduce Crime’ (Psychology Today, April 25th 2018) available at <<https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/crime-and-punishment/201804/why-punishment-doesnt-reduce-crime>> accessed 13th August 2019

¹⁰⁹ Spencer, See n. 15

¹¹⁰ *R v Lowe* [1973] Q.B. 702

¹¹¹ J. Andenaes, ‘Does Punishment Deter Crime?’ in Gertrude Ezorsky (eds), *Philosophical Perspectives on Punishment* (SUNY Press 1972)

¹¹² Spencer, See n. 15

3.4 – The Deterrent

By criminalising certain acts, and punishing offenders, criminal law tries to deter others from acting in the same way. Jensen and Rojek write that “From a deterrence perspective, the criminalisation of an activity is supposed to reduce the involvement of those punished and inhibit involvement in the rest of the population”.¹¹³ The purpose of punishments as deterrence is seen in the case of protection against penalties for medical professionals.¹¹⁴ This theory, in general, provides a field of freedom for medical professionals to obtain protection from criminalisation, i.e., does not give a deterrent to fear of neglect of doctors. This negative aspect of this theory analysis of the idea of the theory in general, but in turn constitutes an important concept about willingly,¹¹⁵ because the patient is willingly agreed to treatment.

The problem is, however, it is hard to see how harsh criminal penalties will deter doctors from making errors. Indeed, the law currently makes no distinction between one-off accidents and systematic ones. It would seem reasonable to try and deter routinely negligent doctors or hospitals with very poor procedures and systems in place. But currently the crime of GNM makes no distinction between that and a fleeting mistake. Indeed, as per the Hamilton report, a large number of respondents “sought to distinguish between genuine errors in medical practice and ‘rule violations’,” arguing “that criminalising errors is not a deterrent and does nothing to prevent the same errors happening again”.¹¹⁶ This is linked to the problem of the lack of definition of ‘gross’ negligence. If the law is trying to deter doctors from ‘gross’ negligence, medical professionals really need to know what ‘gross’ means. And currently they do not, as the issue is left wholly to the jury, as per the Adomako test.¹¹⁷

¹¹³ G F Jensen and D G Rojek, ‘Deterrence and Labeling (From Delinquency and Youth Crime)’ (1992) 6 NCJ P 357,400

¹¹⁴ Andenaes, See n. 111

¹¹⁵ Wolf, See n. 92

¹¹⁶ Hamilton, See n. 17 p.16

¹¹⁷ See n. 39

Garfield writes that the “theory of deterrence rests on free will: one will weigh the criminal sanctions against the benefits derived from committing a particular crime”.¹¹⁸ This does not fit well with the medical profession. In short, no one can dispute that a medical professional, acting in good faith, is trying their very best for the patient. They have a vocation. Using criminal law seems unlikely to deter mistakes. Rather, as discussed later, it is more likely that it will deter them from being medics in the first place.

3.5 - Protection of The Public

A further aim behind whether or not to criminalise a certain activity is to protect the public. This is linked to the harm theory as the law needs to safeguard people from harm. It is also linked to principle of deterrence. According to this idea, it works on what is essential for the protection of the public and it puts a line of protection before the crime, contrary to the theory of the principle of harm, that is, it does not punish a criminal act before it happened, but something moral or otherwise contrary to the principle of society.¹¹⁹

As such, if there is a negative restriction imposed, which does not criminalise anyone in the case where the act did not constitute harm to others,¹²⁰ the lack of a definition by Mills in this theory has also formed a gap in determining what harm is criminalised.¹²¹ Therefore, it seems that the legal protection of the public does not seem to be sufficient in the face of what may be experienced by some medical professionals in the exploitation of harm and covered by treatment.

The Law Commission said that should exist in this theory under the omission principle has been heavily criticized by the law committee as it considers it a danger on the side of manslaughter and should be repaired by codification, and it also does not consider it

¹¹⁸ Garfield L, ‘A More Principled Approach to Criminalizing Negligence: A Prescription for the Legislature’ (1998) 65 Tenn. L. Rev. 875,924

¹¹⁹ Simester, See n. 88

¹²⁰ Ibid

¹²¹ Wilson, See n. 90

satisfactory on the side of manslaughter.¹²² It seems true in terms of criminalisation, but in terms of medical professionals is suitable for what may give them protection and break the fear of be criminalisation within the negligent that may happen in case of some situation out of the control,¹²³ but it certainly scares the public and build the idea that this is a breach of protection for the public.

3.6 - Maintaining a Correct and Functioning Society

A more umbrella theory behind criminal law is based on the need to provide the basis for a decent, correct, fair and functional society.

This seems far from the fact of criminal liability of medical professionals as the doctor will not be in a state of criminal act in the case of gross negligence in manslaughter before it happened, for example, if he tried to treat a patient and almost led to death. It is a known societal principle. In general, this theory seems inappropriate for the criminal responsibility of medical professionals as it focuses on the moral aspect and the impact of society on the criminal law in the determination of criminal responsibility, which may significantly affect the criminalisation of medical professionals when the community sympathy with the patient who died or injured due to the doctor, without taking the form, especially the circumstances surrounding the doctor or the intention that the doctor had.

Indeed, if – as the recent Hamilton report¹²⁴ indicated – doctors are leaving the profession because of the stress and risk of criminalisation, then criminalising their actions will lead to the very opposite of creating a decent, functioning society. Medical practitioners are essential and it is equally essential that they work in good, confident conditions.

¹²² Law Commission, of the draft Criminal Code Bill (Law Com No. 304, 1988) paras 7.13

¹²³ Spencer, See n. 15

¹²⁴ Hamilton, See n. 17 p.16

3.7 - The Theory of Criminal Omissions

Another aspect of criminal theory concerns the approach towards omissions. This criminal principle holds the notion of different legal consequences of positive behavior against omission, the failure to act.¹²⁵

In the Criminal law, omission would constitute a GNM criminal act only in violation of a duty that was necessary. The *R v Adomako* [1995] case constitutes a clear picture of the idea of this principle.¹²⁶ This is highly relevant to the medical profession as many, if not most, acts of negligence will be omissions to act, rather than positive actions. It is obvious that medical practitioners are in a duty of care situation and so are covered by the exception to the general rule that there is no liability for failing to act, only for acting. However, instinctively there seems to be a difference in culpability between a positive act and a failure to act, especially in a medical situation, in a very busy hospital setting. Indeed, opponents point to its failure to deter harm caused by omissions, which is contrary to the principle of criminal laws that are clearly based on the principle of harm, which Feinberg noted as the highest priority of the legal system is life and physical integrity.¹²⁷

This leads us to another aspect of the debate as to what behavior should be criminalised and what should not, namely the importance of *mens rea* and whether negligence, as opposed to intention or recklessness, is capable of being the necessary criminal *men rea*.

3.8 – The Importance of *Mens Rea*

Criminal law is based not only on a guilty action but a guilty mind. The problem with allowing negligence to constitute that guilty mind is that it is based on the principle of reasonableness. Has someone fallen below the standard of the reasonable person? This is a very vague concept. As Stark writes in ‘Criminal Law and Philosophy’, “inculpation

¹²⁵Elliott Catherine, ‘Liability for Manslaughter by Omission: Don't Let the Baby Drown!’ (2010) 74 Journal of Criminal Law 163,179

¹²⁶ See n. 39

¹²⁷ Feinberg, See n. 91

using a vague standard is, indeed, something that the criminal law should avoid where it can. That is one reason not to use negligence liberally in the criminal law”.¹²⁸ It is arguable, therefore, that negligence should not be used to form a basis for criminal liability because criminal sanctions only should be used when people intend the action or the result of the action, or when they knew that that outcome is a probable consequence of the action.¹²⁹

However, others such as Hart¹³⁰ famously believe that there are accepted norms of conduct and that people should be punished if they fall seriously below such standards. The motivation for Hart is largely utilitarian, on the basis that criminalising actions that because harm works well to consciously deter the same specific actions in the future, and to influence people in a general way, more subconsciously, not to do the same but to act in a societal way.

The problem is that accepting a ‘negligent’ *mens rea* might work well for driving offences, a common set of criminal offences where negligence is not really controversial – if you drive carelessly or inattentively and cause harm, then society seems to readily accept that an offence has been committed. But it is not the same for medical negligence. One of the main problems is that “criminal law is ill-equipped to address the complexities of the environment within which health professionals commonly operate – the modern healthcare system”.¹³¹ As McDonald argues, criminal law is based on single agency – the idea that one human act alone and is therefore directly responsible for that action.¹³² This works well for a driver, in control of their car. However, a hospital has a very large number of interconnected people, departments, procedures, timelines, all part of the same process, in a high stress environment; it is difficult to isolate one action in relation to a breach of standard of care. In his work on human error, James Reason writes that “often errors are not the

¹²⁸ Findlay Stark, ‘The Reasonableness in Recklessness’ (2019) 13 Criminal Law and Philosophy 1,24

¹²⁹ J. Hall, ‘Negligent Behaviour should be Excluded from Penal Liability’ (1963) 63 Colum. L. Rev. 632

¹³⁰ H.L.A. Hart, ‘Punishment and Responsibility: Essays in the Philosophy of Law’, (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1968); H.L.A. Hart, “Negligence, *Mens Rea* and Criminal Responsibility” in A.G. Guest, ed., ‘Oxford Essays in Jurisprudence: A Collaborative Work’ (London: Oxford University Press, 1961) at 29

¹³¹ McDonald Fiona, ‘The criminalisation of medical mistakes in Canada: a review’ (2008) 16 Health Law Journal 1,25

¹³² *Ibid.* p.4

outcome of individual incompetence but are created by factors inherent to the complex system within which that individual works”.¹³³

3.9 - Conclusion

In conclusion, which acts society choses to criminalise, and which not, is a complex operation. Harm seems a general pre-requisite and is easily established in medical negligence cases. However, there must be more. A moral core is needed so that if the act is not made criminal then it would go against the morals of society and there would be outrage. The desire for retribution seems relevant, the fact that someone should pay for the unnecessary loss, especially that of a child. However, this fits far less well with genuine errors made by caring and professional medics. Nor is the deterrent argument convincing, indeed added stress being likely to endanger patient safety more than improve the standard. Nor the need to protect the public - these are not chronically useless doctors but ones that simply commit a one-off serious error. Indeed, using negligence and the standard of the reasonable man for criminal law is fraught with problems. When Justice Holmes wrote that “the true purpose of the criminal law is to coerce individuals to conform their behavior to societal norms”,¹³⁴ it seems unlikely he meant we should be ‘coercing’ well-intentioned doctors to behave as society lays down that doctors should behave. The next chapter will therefore analyse if a different approach would serve better.

¹³³ James Reason, *Human Error* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1990)

¹³⁴ Oliver W. Holmes, Jr., ‘Theories of Punishment and the External Standard’, in Abraham S. Goldstein & Joseph Goldstein (eds), *Crime, Law and Society* (Free Press 1971)

Chapter 4 – Legal Controversies Regarding GNM and Medical Professionals

After having looked at the basic requirements of the crime of GNM and the theoretical reasons for criminalising certain behaviours, it is now important to look at legal controversies in the law itself and at practical considerations. It is clear that GNM is currently applied to, and results in a criminalisation of medical professionals. However, as shown, this criminalisation is based on rather dubious theories, creating a situation that is arguably unfair to medical professionals. Indeed, with several very high-profile cases in the past decade, there has been much argument, both in academia and the medical profession, as to whether the law achieves what it sets out to achieve. Two important reports have also been published in the past year to tackle these concerns. This chapter will analyse both the legal problems and the most important policy issues regarding GNM as applied to medical practitioners.

4.1 - Foresight of Harm

The main issue in the law of GNM is still the '*mens rea*' that is required. As has been shown, for GNM itself, there is no requirement for intention, nor even recklessness. As opposed to a subjective standard, like in the vast majority of crimes, the question is an objective one: did the accused fall below the standard of the reasonable man in their duty of care situation?

The reasonable man standard seems important to apply and this is due to several reasons, the simplest of which is the different situations in the status of a doctor to another, as well as a difference in the state of the disease. However, there remains the subject of the duty of care that the medical professional had to provide and the extent of the breach has to be clear, and whether this constitutes recklessness by doctor for the patient.

When dealing with foresight to harm, the case of *R v Adomako* [1995]¹³⁵ is clearly insightful when he did not look after any interest in the respiratory system that had stopped,

¹³⁵ See n. 39

nor any of the signs that any doctor under the standard should be the reasonable person will pay attention to them. Therefore, the most important issue is a question that must be asked by the jury of the accused, as happened in a case of *Rex v Murphy* (1914),¹³⁶ when the jury questioned, would he do what the reasonable [person] did?

There was, therefore, no requirement of foresight of harm by the doctor in the Adomako test. This was the position of the Law Commission in 2006 as well. At para 3.59, the report writes that:

“Gross negligence manslaughter can be committed even when D was unaware that his or her conduct might cause death, or even injury. This is because negligence, however gross, does not necessarily involve any actual realisation that one is posing a risk of harm: it is a question of how glaringly obvious the risk would have been to a reasonable person”¹³⁷

As such, the medical practitioner can be guilty, without any realization of the potential harm of his/her actions. That, however, was found to be unfair compared to the *R v Rose* [2017]¹³⁸ case, where, despite the court of first instance, it is now established in the Court of Appeal that the serious risk of death must have been actually known/foreseeable to the accused, not just ought to have been known. This brings a subjective element into the normal objective negligence test. As such, the range of guilty situations is reduced and only applies where the doctor realized the serious risk, and still acted in a way that grossly breached their duty of care.

¹³⁶ *Rex v Murphy*, 49 Ir. L. T. Rep. 15, 208 (1914)

¹³⁷ Law Commission, *Murder, Manslaughter and Infanticide* (Law Com No. 304, 2006) paras 3.59

¹³⁸ See n. 4

However, this is almost worse: it means that a good doctor who can foresee the harm would be guilty, whereas an utterly useless doctor who had no idea what they were doing is harmful would not be guilty. Mullock writes in the Medical Law Review that:

“in more complex cases where the serious risk of death is not immediately obvious, negligently failing to assess risk seems to prevent potential liability on the basis that the putative defendant was in a position of negligent ignorance.”¹³⁹

Surely this is not the desired outcome. Rather than limiting criminalization, as Rose case aimed to do, it simply limits criminalization of *bad* doctors. Indeed, the doctor in the Honey Rose case was effectively not guilty because she did *not* do a test that a competent and responsible doctor would have done. The Court’s justification was that ‘actual’ knowledge was different from ‘putative’ knowledge and that, as a matter of policy, if the conviction were upheld, doctors failing to undertake a whole range of medical tests could be guilty of GNM.¹⁴⁰ This, however, seems to be missing the point. If by failing to order the test, the doctor has seriously breached their duty of care, then that is grossly negligent in itself. Rather, by finding that Dr. Rose was not guilty precisely because she had not ordered the test, and therefore had no knowledge of harm, (whereas she would have been guilty if she had ordered the test and not acted on it), there is a clear message to medical practitioners *not* to order tests. As Mullock writes, this is hardly conducive to patient safety.¹⁴¹ The Court’s desire to protect doctors from over-criminalisation is therefore not ill-placed but the method of doing so has left the potential for ridiculous legal situations.

It should also be noted that the subjective element of actual foresight of harm introduced in Rose case was effectively rejected in *R v Winterton* [2018]¹⁴² or, at least, distinguished on the rather dubious basis that, objectively, the doctor seemingly did not necessarily see

¹³⁹ Mullock, See n. 10

¹⁴⁰ *R v Rose* [2018] 2 All ER 430

¹⁴¹ Mullock, See n. 10

¹⁴² *R v Winterton* [2018] EWCA Crim 2435

the risk but the construction site manager must have done. The courts' desire to 'help' doctors is understandable but does not necessarily create good law.

4.2 - 'Gross' Negligence

The negligence in GNM has to be 'gross' as per the Bateman test, as discussed previously. Although the *mens rea* is one aspect, the question of what really constitutes reprehensible, truly criminal behavior, with 'such disregard' for life, is a broad question, and a problematic one. The negligent fact is based on the mere naturalistic result, disregarding, as such, the devaluation of the action. With the doctrine of the final action, advocated by Dekker,¹⁴³ based on the illegality of the negligent fact in the devaluation of the conduct. From this moment on, criminal legal dogma began to develop the doctrine of the negligent fact as a problem of the type and not of causality.¹⁴⁴

Based on that to prevent others from making the same mistake in the future, the punishment of a doctors causing a patient's medical mistake is dependent on his previous suspected precedent, which may actually prevent the mistake.¹⁴⁵ However, the use of the same directing to guilt the medical professionals from case to another it seems not right, with the different circumstances and in case of recklessness and gross negligence. The use of criminal law is almost always productive in identifying and addressing the cause of the error,¹⁴⁶ but the criminal system has to be more flexible in terms of different cases of criminalizing medical professionals because not all cases similar in the gross negligence.

¹⁴³ Dekker Sidney, *Just Culture: Balancing Safety and Accountability* (2nd edn, CRC Press 2016)

¹⁴⁴ Andrew Ashworth. 'Positive duties, regulation and the criminal sanction.' (2017) 133 *Law Quarterly Review* 606,630

¹⁴⁵ Hanoch Dagan, and Avihay Dorfman, 'Substantive Remedies.' (SSRN, 27 Jan 2019) Available at <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3316125?> accessed 27 August 2019

¹⁴⁶ Mulheron Rachael, *Medical Negligence: Non-patient and Third Party Claims* (1st edn, Routledge 2016).

4.2.1 - The Jury – How Do They Decide?

Because of this lack of definition of ‘gross’, there is a serious problem. It is normal for the judge to direct the jury on the points of law required to make their decision. However, in the case of GNM, the direction boils down to effectively was the behavior of the medical professional so serious as to be criminalised, if so, the jury may find the doctor guilty. As Lord Mackay of Clashfern LC said, after following the *R v Adomako [1995]* case, when deciding whether a doctor is guilty of the offence of GNM, the judge gives three points to the jury to established, the last being 'the jury have to consider whether that breach was of such a serious nature as to be characterised as gross negligence and therefore as a crime'.¹⁴⁷ This is not a guideline, it has no legal direction, nothing that can be used for different juries to obtain some degree of consistency. It is direction based on the ‘gut feel’ of the jury.

The Court of Appeal rejected this inherent inconsistency and lack of clarity as being an issue in *Misra*, but, as Lodge says, did so ‘unpersuasively’.¹⁴⁸ This problem was highlighted in *Sellu v The Crown [2016]*¹⁴⁹ where the doctor’s conviction for GNM was overturned in the Court of Appeal. To decide if the negligence was sufficiently ‘gross’, the Crown court judge had simply instructed the jury to use “their own common and good sense to decide whether the line has been crossed”.¹⁵⁰ Furthermore, testimony from medical experts was admitted, indeed encouraged, regarding whether it constituted truly serious negligence. The judge did not remind the jury that it was their decision, not the experts. When the jury asked for further help, none was given. As such, the conviction was unsafe because the jury were badly directed. Following this case, McDonald and Vaughan write, “judges must now direct juries much more tightly”¹⁵¹ and experts cannot usurp the role of

¹⁴⁷ See n. 39

¹⁴⁸ Lodge, See n. 26

¹⁴⁹ See n. 22

¹⁵⁰ Ibid. para 77

¹⁵¹ Peter McDonald and Jenny Vaughan, ‘The aftermath of the Sellu case for law and the medical profession’ (2018) 100 The Bulletin of The Royal College of Surgeons of England 207,209

law. However, what exactly that direction should be is still not clear and the case highlights the mess that the law is in.¹⁵²

In short, as per the very recent Archbold Review, Spencer believes that the real problem lies not only in the current law and the nature of the crime, but in the lack of guidance to the jury, and the complete lack of clarity of what standard is needed, from very minor honest error up to complete disregard and recklessness. As he writes:

“If, as in the *Bawa-Garba* case, the jury thinks a simple error of professional judgement satisfies the test, the result is a conviction: appeal proof, if the jury was properly directed.”¹⁵³

As Tom Bingham argues, the law is supposed to offer a degree of predictability, of certainty. The rule of law, the basis for all democratic countries, says that law should not be arbitrary or unclear.¹⁵⁴ This is hardly the case, given the continued lack of jury directions in GNM.

4.3 - Single Agency Culpability and Human Error

Criminalising one doctor for a serious error that is part of a whole complex situation is not a fair use of criminal law. Besides, it is important to distinguish between one-time slippages and a major violation by medical professionals, this constitutes a significant difference in medical practices and criminalisation.¹⁵⁵ It is also illogical and unfair to criminalise both the doctor who made a one-time mistake and the doctor who works with recklessness and disrespect for the duty of care. It is not possible to say that the two cases are similar, which may occur in medical cases that are to culpable for parties other than the doctor around him. Merry and McCall Smith write that a simple human error is in no way the same as a

¹⁵² J.R. Spencer, ‘Criminal Liability for Negligence – A Lesson from Across the Channel?’ (2010) 59 *International and Comparative Law Journal* 1,24

¹⁵³ Spencer, See n. 15

¹⁵⁴ Tom Bingham, *The Rule of Law* (first published by Allen Lane 2010, Penguin 2011)

¹⁵⁵ Alan Merry and Alexander, S. McCall, *Errors, Medicine and the Law* (1st edn, Cambridge University Press 2001)

‘violation’ where an error comes from “a conscious decision by the medical professional to disobey an accepted rule of proper practice.”¹⁵⁶ This is particularly important given the high stress features of medical practice. The writers make the distinction of failing to notice a dislodged breathing tube (as in Adomako case¹⁵⁷) and having inserted the breathing tube incorrectly, against normal practice, in the first place. However, the current law on GNM fails to see a difference.

Furthermore, criminal law is based on the principle of single agency culpability. The person who commits the *actus reus*, with the appropriate *mens rea*, is guilty of the crime. Although duress and necessity are acknowledged as two defences, the essential starting point is, as per the House of Lords, that “informed adults of sound mind are treated as autonomous beings able to make their own decisions how they will act”.¹⁵⁸ However, this fails to take into account the very complex situations in medical centres and hospitals. Obviously, all the medical practitioners are free individuals, responsible for their actions. But, in the Bawa Garber case, for instance, many doctors are effectively forced to work extremely long hours, in high-stress environments. Many are not supported properly by management, under extreme pressure to cut costs and meet strict time guidelines. It is hardly their ‘fault’ if human errors are more common in this environment. And yet the criminalisation is 100% directed to the specific doctor, not the Hospital Board, or management. This does not seem to reflect modern practice.

Indeed, the current criminal law and its criminalization system may weaken the anger, and feeling of justice for the patient's parents,¹⁵⁹ but also what is needed is an investigation to find out what has actually happened, not to culpabilise the medical professionals for the supposed crime. The *Bawa-Garba (Hadiza) [2016]*¹⁶⁰ case is the clearest picture of this single culpability for the doctor in the event of a medical error, showing the existence of

¹⁵⁶ Merry, See n. 155

¹⁵⁷ See n. 39

¹⁵⁸ R v Kennedy [2007] UKHL 38

¹⁵⁹ Spencer, See n. 15

¹⁶⁰ See n. 5

circumstances around them, including lack of medical staff and delay of diagnosis. In general, if a doctor does not follow the usual practice and causes an error, the doctor may not have fulfilled the duty of care and should be regarded as negligent,¹⁶¹ but the criminal law has to put an end to the single culpability of the medical professional to protect them from over-criminalisation.

4.3.1 – The Need for Reform: The Williams and Hamilton Reports

The very recent Williams and Hamilton reports respond to public and professional concern that medical practitioners are being unfairly persecuted, with bad effect, and are part of an acknowledgment that reform is needed in the criminal law to protect the medical professionals. The reports do not fall within their competence or powers to work on a change of the law as stated in the report of Williams 2018 “This review was not set up to recommend changes in the law but to look at how decisions are made within the current legal framework”.¹⁶² Nevertheless, it would be useful to take into account the reports’ findings.

According to the Williams report into GNM in healthcare settings, the legal bar is set “appropriately high”¹⁶³ following the Rose case. However, there are serious problems with consistency, and with investigations being carried out with very little chance of a case being brought, based also on a lack of consistent guidelines and understanding. This is very disruptive and not conducive to good patient care. It also ties in with the problems identified above as regards the lack of legal guidelines to juries regarding ‘gross’ negligence. It is certainly true, however, that the medical professionals have not to be above the law. In the same context, therefore, one of the recommendations made by the report was to find a clear position to criminalize medical professionals in the crime of gross

¹⁶¹ See n. 5

¹⁶² Williams, See n. 16 p.9

¹⁶³ Williams, See n. 16 para 6.2

negligence, in order to promote a clear understanding of where to begin the charge of gross negligence.

The Hamilton report is extremely recent, commissioned by the GMC and published only a couple of months ago in June 2019,¹⁶⁴ to respond to what is called the ‘toxic fear’ in the profession following the high profile medical GNM cases.¹⁶⁵ It is not a report on the law but on the negative effect that criminalization of medical practitioners is having on the profession. However, it is based on that negative effect that there are calls for the law to change. A large number of respondents “sought to distinguish between genuine errors in medical practice and ‘rule violations’,” arguing “that criminalising errors is not a deterrent and does nothing to prevent the same errors happening again”.¹⁶⁶ This linked to the issue that if the law is trying to deter medical professionals from gross negligence really need to add the recklessness to it, that will be fair because the rule violations is close to being another face of recklessness, and currently they do not, as the issue is left wholly to the jury, as per the Adomako test.¹⁶⁷ The reform sought here, as the report may suggest, is to find a way to reassure medical professionals by identifying what might protect them if they are accused of gross negligence, which may not have occurred because of their recklessness or intent. This suggests reform Spencer¹⁶⁸ mentioned, as previously referenced, it certainly alleviates the fear of medical professionals who have become fearful of criminal responsibility, because of a mistake that could occur.

4.3.2 - Recklessness Test and Gross Negligence

One of the main legal controversies is whether recklessness should be required as part of the *mens rea*. Indeed, following the House of Lords in *R v Seymour*[1983],¹⁶⁹ the general

¹⁶⁴ Hamilton, See n. 17

¹⁶⁵ Ibid. p.3

¹⁶⁶ Ibid. p.16

¹⁶⁷ See n. 39

¹⁶⁸ Spencer, See n. 15

¹⁶⁹ See n. 36

approach was that Caldwell recklessness was necessary for GNM.¹⁷⁰ And, over time, many judges have used recklessness almost interchangeably with negligence: in the Lamb case [1967],¹⁷¹ to take just one example, Sachs LJ writes about "criminal negligence - often referred to as recklessness". It is true that the Court of Appeal then rejected this approach in Prentice¹⁷² but in 2005, the Law Commission wrote that "recklessness falling short of reckless indifference can really be regarded as a kind of gross negligence",¹⁷³ which just continues the confusion. Certainly, if left to the layman without direction, it is obvious that many people will not see a distinction and recklessness will usually be incorporated via the jury's interpretation of 'gross' negligence, even if not specifically required under the law.¹⁷⁴

The recklessness test in case of *R v Lawrence* [1981],¹⁷⁵ concerning an accident caused by recklessness in a traffic accident, is arguably, therefore, an appropriate measure to be used to criminalise medical professionals, because the defendant - the doctor - must have predicted a clear risk or failed to predict the possibility of a risk, which is recklessness of the medical professional.¹⁷⁶ Charging doctors with GNM, which was not in a state of recklessness, fails to protect sufficiently the doctors because there are a lot of medical errors that occur as a result beyond the doctor's control, resulting in over-criminalisation. Just as this test has been approved by the House of Lords and applied in the *R v Seymour* [1983]¹⁷⁷ case, in this situation this test of recklessness may be associated with negligence, so it appears that its application to cases of GNM of medical professionals will be suitable.

Quick also makes a convincing argument for the introduction of subjective recklessness as a requirement for the offence.¹⁷⁸

¹⁷⁰ Law Commission, *Involuntary Manslaughter* (Law Com No 135, 1994) para 3.59

¹⁷¹ *R v Lamb* [1967] 2 QB 981

¹⁷² See n. 37

¹⁷³ Law Commission, *A New Homicide Act for England and Wales* (Consultation Paper No. 177, 2005), p. 90, para 3.182.

¹⁷⁴ Quick, See n. 3

¹⁷⁵ *R v Lawrence* [1981] 1 All ER 974

¹⁷⁶ Stephen Griffin, 'Corporate Manslaughter: A Radical Reform?' (2007) 71 *Journal of Criminal Law* 151

¹⁷⁷ See n. 36

¹⁷⁸ Quick, See n. 3

4.4 - Conclusion

The current situation of GNM in the healthcare setting is a practical problem as well as a legal one. Doctors feel vulnerable, and patient care is threatened. The ‘blame culture’ is ‘symptomatic of the embattlement’¹⁷⁹ that many medics experience on a daily basis. The single agency culpability approach of English criminal law is a serious problem: The Lancet highlights the “continuing failure within the GMC and criminal justice system to appreciate the importance of systems and human factors that are crucial for an increasingly stretched National Health Service”.¹⁸⁰ Doctors acting intentionally or recklessly below the level required would seem to easily fit a personal fault theory. Even failing to follow correct procedures might fit the same category. However, for single, one-off mistakes, so linked to the frantic mayhem of many medical settings, it is difficult to see how or why one medic should be singled out as a criminal. Furthermore, the legal requirement for foresight of harm is untenable, given the effective loophole it gives poor doctors.

¹⁷⁹ Hamilton, See n. 17 p.3

¹⁸⁰ The Lancet, ‘Gross negligence manslaughter’ (The Lancet, 22 June 2019) available at <<https://www.thelancet.com/action/showPdf?pii=S0140-6736%2819%2931407-2>> accessed 3 September 2019

Chapter 5 – Conclusion

As the Law Commission stated in 1994, the problem with GNM is that “it is virtually impossible to identify any governing principles or policy” underlying the law.¹⁸¹ Indeed, the report states the law is in a ‘deplorable’ state.¹⁸² Unfortunately, 25 years later, little has changed. For the medical profession this is exacerbated even further as the current law makes no distinction between the medical professional and others. Mistakes, even negligent ones, occur in all fields, but the medical field is high risk, high stress, and its main aim is to do good: there is a need, therefore, for no over-criminalization of doctors. Doctors suffer from the pressure of work and errors/shortfalls that are in the medical facility itself, as happened in the Bawa-Garber case.¹⁸³ It is unfair, unhelpful and counter-productive for medical professionals to be criminalized for an action that is not a stand-alone criminal act but part of a bigger picture, perhaps, of systematic failure.

GNM, after all, is part of general manslaughter and one of the most serious offences, with a maximum sentence of life imprisonment. Justice minister, Rory Stewart, stated: “Manslaughter is an extremely serious offence, causing immeasurable pain to families who lose their loved ones”.¹⁸⁴ GNM, though, has often been treated more leniently. However, sentencing guidelines for GNM have recently been changed, as of 1st November 2018, to increase the normal custodial sentences.¹⁸⁵ Even at the lowest level of culpability (where “The negligent conduct was a lapse in the offender’s otherwise satisfactory standard of care”,¹⁸⁶ which seems applicable to most medical GNM cases) the guidelines call for 2-4 years imprisonment. This is a career-ending and life-changing result for a doctor. Nor are the numbers negligible: between 1990 and 2006, over 50 medical practitioners have been

¹⁸¹ Law Commission, ‘Involuntary Manslaughter’, Consultation Paper, (Law Com No 135, 1994) paras 1.24

¹⁸² *Ibid*

¹⁸³ See n. 5

¹⁸⁴ Owen Bowcott, ‘Gross negligence manslaughter jail terms could rise in England and Wales’ *The guardian* (London, 31 Jul 2018) available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/law/2018/jul/31/gross-negligence-manslaughter-jail-terms-rise-england-wales> accessed 6 September 2019

¹⁸⁵ Sentencing Council, *Manslaughter Definitive Guideline* (Published on 31 July 2018)

¹⁸⁶ *Ibid.* p.10

charged with GNM.¹⁸⁷ The stress and bad feeling that this causes, and the detrimental effect on work atmosphere, even patient safety, is acknowledged in all the literature, the Hamilton report calling it ‘palpable and profound’.¹⁸⁸

It is for this reason that reform is needed. Husak writes that over-criminalisation can only be dealt with effectively at the prosecution level.¹⁸⁹ The Williams report makes a similar point where it asks for the bar to be set at a level where, as a matter of policy, prosecutions are only brought in “rare cases where an individual’s performance is so “truly exceptionally bad” that it requires a criminal sanction”.¹⁹⁰ However, this leaves too much uncertainty as the prosecutor would still have to effectively second guess the juries’ interpretation of ‘gross’ negligence, which leads back to the same problem that there is no definition of ‘criminal’ negligence, no definition of ‘exceptionally bad’,¹⁹¹ no meaningful “route to verdict”.¹⁹²

Others, such as Quick, discuss the pros and cons of a specific statute, a ‘Dangerous Doctors Act’, so to speak.¹⁹³ This would give codification but, as Spencer highlights, approaching law reform by a ‘binge’ approach of new law-making is seldom the answer.¹⁹⁴

Another radical reform would be to abolish GNM altogether. The UK’s Offences Against the Person Act 1861 does not include negligence, just intent and recklessness¹⁹⁵. Many crimes are result-dependent but the lesser result still is a criminal offense (i.e. GBH that results in death is murder, otherwise still GBH). In this case, however, it is difficult to see why one action that results in death should be criminal but the exact same action that causes lifelong injury should not be criminal at all. Professor Spencer calls this a ‘grave

¹⁸⁷ R. Ferner and S. McDowell ‘Doctors charged with manslaughter in the course of medical practice, 1795–2005: a literature review’ (2006) 99 *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine* 309

¹⁸⁸ Hamilton, See n. 17 para 40

¹⁸⁹ Douglas Husak, *Overcriminalization: The Limits of the Criminal Law* (1st edn, Oxford University Press 2009)

¹⁹⁰ Williams, See n. 16 para 2.4

¹⁹¹ Lodge, See n. 26

¹⁹² See n. 22

¹⁹³ Quick, See n. 3

¹⁹⁴ J.R. Spencer, ‘The Drafting of Criminal Justice Legislation — Need it be so Impenetrable?’ (2008) *C.L.J.* 585

¹⁹⁵ See n. 106

anomaly'.¹⁹⁶ However, it is unlikely that abolition would be popular: as discussed under 'public outrage', people would not readily accept the death of a child being 'unpunishable'. Rather, one possible reform would be for GNM to recognise the logical distinction between negligence due to specifically not following normal procedures, and negligence from a human error in following those procedures. Doctors and health care workers are responsible for caring for patients, not for curing every patient. Many treatments or surgeries are not consistent with universal and approved treatment procedures.¹⁹⁷ However, in general, as long as the doctor acts according to generally approved procedures, even if other doctors' treatment may differ, or even if errors are made, the doctor should not be regarded as criminally negligent for such an error. If a doctor does not follow the usual practice and causes death, GNM seems more appropriate. This would enable the judge to give clear directions to the jury and thus render "results that are consistent and predictable",¹⁹⁸ as per the rule of law.¹⁹⁹

This would also help tackle the problem of single agency culpability. One of the arguments for reducing the blame for medical professionals and seeking some sort of criminal responsibility by the law in distribution to those who were part of it, is Samanta's argument that accountability and responsibility should be appropriately divided between health care systems, managers and doctors, rather than leaving the individual to bear all the blame.²⁰⁰ Single agency culpability needs to be reformed in distributing the burden of medical error that may occur due to negligence of those who have work in health care. It is important to distinguish between one-time slippages and a major violation by medical professionals.²⁰¹ However, this would mean that systematic problems would either be a defence for GNM, making the medical practitioner not guilty if he/she can prove there were managerial errors that contributed to the breach of duty. The range of managerial errors,

¹⁹⁶ Spencer, See n. 152, p.4

¹⁹⁷ Castiglioni Arturo, '*A History of Medicine*', (1st edn, Routledge 2019)

¹⁹⁸ Spencer, See n. 15

¹⁹⁹ Bingham, See n. 154

²⁰⁰ Samanta, See n. 7

²⁰¹ Merry, See n. 155

though, is vase and it would be very difficult to decide where fault began. Or that the doctor would be jointly liable with the health trust and corporate manslaughter would have to be balanced with individual doctor GNM. However, this balancing of blame seems far more suited to civil law than criminal law.

The answer, therefore, may be to require recklessness as a pre-requisite for GNM. Quick from Bristol University makes a strong argument for subjective recklessness.²⁰² Based on interviews with prosecutors, he claims that this is, in effect, what happens in practice.²⁰³ Brudner also says that, legally if not morally, criminalisation requires a conscious choice to harm or risk harm that is 'self-willed by the criminal and so consonant with his inviolability'.²⁰⁴ However, even this does not really get round the foresight of harm problem that the courts have created following Rose case where a truly poor doctor may not be guilty whereas a reasonable one would because, subjectively, doctors are not reckless if they do not act in a way they see to be dangerous. Therefore, the appropriate justification for criminalizing medical professionals, according to what appears to be objective recklessness in GNM, is perhaps the most appropriate as recommended. One method would be to use the Caldwell/Lawrence test of recklessness in the *R v Lawrence* [1981]²⁰⁵ case. Recklessness here in GNM is recklessly as a medical professional in such a way that it is less than the standard of the reasonable medical man. The Williams' report recommendations seem very useful here, namely to improve consistency in GNM by developing the role of experts with clinical experience.²⁰⁶ The House of Lords in *Seymour* [1983]²⁰⁷ accepted objective recklessness as the necessary standard for manslaughter, not negligence, and, although the courts have since moved away from this, it has much to recommend it. However, punishing inadvertent, unconscious risk-taking is a problem.²⁰⁸

²⁰² Quick, See n. 3

²⁰³ O.L. Quick, 'Prosecuting 'Gross' Medical Negligence: Manslaughter, Discretion and the Crown Prosecution Service' (2006) 33 *Journal of Law and Society* 421,450

²⁰⁴ A. Brudner, 'Subjective Fault for Crime: A Reinterpretation' (2008) 14 *Legal Theory* 1, 38

²⁰⁵ See n. 175

²⁰⁶ Williams, See n. 16 para 2.4

²⁰⁷ See n. 36

²⁰⁸ Lodge, See n. 26

It should be noted that, in terms of this research, the pressure for legal change is very strong and very current. As of writing, there has not been time to gauge the professional reaction to the GMC's very recent and detailed June 2019 independent report. Further caselaw developments are also expected, given the reaction to the recent high-profile cases.

In short, medical errors cannot be subject to a uniform criminalization of GNM as 'medical mistakes come in many shapes and sizes yet criminal law adopts a one size fits all approach'.²⁰⁹ The law should be more flexible its approach to criminalizing gross negligence in manslaughter for medical professionals. The aim is not to lift the legal barrier and make doctors above the law, but to seek to not over-criminalize medicals professionals. This will certainly help alleviate the fear of medical professionals of criminalisation, which discourages well-intentioned, professional doctors from doing their job and creates risks for patient safety. Crucial action is needed to "ensure that conscientious doctors are no longer prosecuted for honest errors of professional judgement made when working under stress."²¹⁰

²⁰⁹ Quick, See n. 3

²¹⁰ Spencer, See n. 15

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